

Failure of suprathreshold electrical stimuli to evoke 1:1 nerve firing in intraneural recordings: effect of stimulation current

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Abstract. In haptics and prosthetics applications of electrical stimulation, axons are often assumed to consistently respond to increasing stimulation frequencies, i.e. axons that fire at 10 Hz in response to 10 Hz stimulation should respond at 100 Hz to 100 Hz stimulation. We recorded intraneural compound action potentials (CAP) in healthy human participants. There was a rapid decline in CAP amplitudes within 0.2s of stimulus onset, suggesting that the axon population is not reliably responding; with greater decline at higher stimulation frequencies. These findings have significant implications for electrical nerve stimulation in haptics.

Keywords: Electrical stimulation, compound action potential, sensory feedback

1 Background

Electrical nerve stimulation is commonly applied in haptics under the assumption [1, 2] that 1 suprathreshold stimulus pulse consistently evokes 1 action potential in responding nerve axons (1:1 following). It was recently reported that electrical stimulation of residual axons in amputees cannot convey frequency information above 50 Hz [3]. We tested the assumption of 1:1 following at electrical stimulation frequencies up to 150 Hz. The effect of higher (150%) electrical current in preceding stimuli was also tested on subsequent responses to stimuli delivered at base (100%) current.

2 Methods

Intraneural CAP recordings were performed using wrist median nerve microneurography in healthy humans. Protocols were approved by the UNSW Sydney human research ethics committee (HC210271). CAP amplitudes served as a measure of responses to digital nerve electrical stimulation. Base current was defined as current 1 mA above that evoking CAP amplitude $>20 \mu\text{V}$ (found by increasing current in 0.5 mA steps for 10 Hz stimuli). The effect of stimulation frequency (25-150 Hz) on 1:1 following was

tested at 100% base current (Fig. 1a). The effect of stimulation current on subsequent responses was tested with 10s 100 Hz conditioning at 100% base or 150% base (high) current; followed by 1s 10Hz test and 1min 0.2Hz recovery at base current (Fig. 1b).

Fig. 1. Parameters for intraneural CAP recordings. **a)** Effect of stimulation frequency on 1:1 axon following. **b)** Effect of stimulation current: ongoing and subsequent axon responsiveness.

3 Results

CAP amplitudes declined rapidly within 0.2s of stimulation onset (Fig. 2a).

Fig. 2. a) Mean CAP amplitudes (shaded region \pm 95% CI, $n = 13$) in response to 10s stimulation: greater declines in CAP amplitude at higher frequencies. Values downsampled to match 25 Hz sampling intervals for visual compatibility. Amplitudes normalised to first CAP response amplitude at each stimulation frequency (set to 1) for each fascicle. **b)** Effect of current on responses to conditioning (dashed lines) and subsequent test ‘o’ and recovery ‘+’ stimulation. For each fascicle, conditioning response amplitudes were normalised to first conditioning CAP response at the respective current. As test and recovery stimuli used base current, responses were normalised to first conditioning response at base current. Means plotted, shaded region \pm 95% CI ($n = 6$).

After 10s stimulation (Fig. 2a), CAP amplitudes declined $32 \pm 10\%$ for 25 Hz ($21 \pm 9\%$ after 0.2s of stimulation, mean \pm 95% CI), $51 \pm 9\%$ ($32 \pm 9\%$) for 50 Hz, $60 \pm 12\%$ ($41 \pm 11\%$) for 100 Hz and $68 \pm 8\%$ ($54 \pm 9\%$) for 150 Hz. CAP amplitudes declined less with high (150% base) current (Fig. 2b, pink dashed line). However, this was followed by a prolonged reduction in responsiveness to stimulation delivered at base current for the next minute (response amplitudes after conditioning at high current: pink o and +; green denotes responses after conditioning at base current).

4 Conclusion

Axons increasingly failed to reliably respond to higher electrical stimulation frequencies. Higher stimulation current alleviated this, but led to slower recovery and greater decline for subsequent stimuli at lower current. Our findings suggest that electrical stimulation in haptics may not evoke reliable 1:1 following in responding axons.

Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange. We invite discussions regarding computational modelling of nerve following rates in response to electrical stimulation, and psychophysics regarding evoked perceptual qualities such as frequency or intensity.

Acknowledgments. Research supported by Australian Research Council (DP200100630). A.S. is supported by an Australian Government Research Training Program Scholarship.

Disclosure of Interests. Authors declare no conflicts of interest, financial or otherwise.

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